

Hyperion

D9.3 Dissemination and Communication Plan

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¹ **R**=Document, report; **DEM**=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC**=website, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**=other

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ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

AB	Advisory board
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Climate Change
CH	Cultural Heritage
CoP	Communities of Practices
CDP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
GA	Grant Agreement
GPL	General Public License
HRAP	Holistic Risk Assessment Platform
ICCS	Institute of Communications and Computer Systems
IEMC	Intercultural Euro-Mediterranean Center for UNESCO
PC	Project Coordinator
PCT	Project Coordination Team
PM	Project Manager
QM	Quality Manager
QP	Quality Plan
RG	Resilience Guard GmbH
WP	Work Package
SG	Structural/Geotechnical (tool)
PET	Privacy Enhancing Technologies

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Executive Summary

The aim of this deliverable (D9.3) is to address how HYPERION project will manage various issues related to the dissemination and communication of the project. The present dissemination and communication plan outlines the identification of different stakeholders and the respective strategy devised, the different communication and dissemination tools adopted, along with specific actions foreseen to address any issues relating to the benefits of an **integrated resilience assessment platform**, focusing on multi-hazard risk understanding, better preparedness, faster, adapted and efficient response, and **sustainable reconstruction** of historic areas; to disseminate results of HYPERION project; and to raise citizens awareness and policy makers implication.

Communication and Dissemination (and later Exploitation) is essential to turn the project's work into well-spread results.

In the project proposal, HYPERION team set ambitious targets for the project's communication and dissemination plan and respective activities. This report sets out the strategy and plan designed in detail in order to achieve these targets. Each of HYPERION project partners will allocate time for dissemination and has an important role to play in the successful communication and dissemination of the project.

Partners have already demonstrated their commitment in the six months following the kick-off of the project.

Although the Communication and Dissemination Plan is a deliverable to be submitted by the sixth month of HYPERION project, it will be regularly reviewed and updated to ensure that its objectives are met and amended, if and when necessary. The targets and measurements will be reviewed regularly as the project evolves.

1. INTRODUCTION

The current Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) – prepared through the Dissemination, Communication and Standardization Activities Work Package (WP9) – will ensure that all communication and dissemination requests, from various WPs and the project in general, are taken into consideration and are effectively coordinated.

The main objective is to present a coherent plan and make a constructive contribution to implementing and delivering high impact communication and dissemination activities that cover the actions taken from the very start of the project, actions planned for different stages of the project as well as continuous activities running throughout the lifetime of the project.

This document thus is made to ensure that clear communication objectives have been set, that key target audiences have been identified and well defined, that tailored messages have been crafted per each target audience, that the appropriate channels will be used, that sufficient communication materials and resources will be produced and that the right evaluation methods will be implemented.

Moreover, it contains all the important information needed to facilitate the communication efforts of the HYPERION consortium. It presents the HYPERION project's dissemination and communication strategy and its implementation plan that is being used by the consortium in order to guarantee high visibility, accessibility and promotion of the project's vision, key findings and research results. HYPERION is highly dependent on well-organized and implemented communication and dissemination activities.

It is the reference framework for monitoring and evaluating the impact of communication and dissemination activities and will be updated once again (**M42**) before the project end. It will remain as a key mechanism to ensure the adequate progress of the project, to produce the envisaged results, and to successfully achieve the fundamental goals all through HYPERION's life circle.

The management and overall implementation of Dissemination and Communication activities is led by **IEMC** (WP9 leader and the leader of Tasks 9.1-9.4.). **RG** (Leader of Task 9.5) and **ICCS** (Project Coordinator) also play strategic role in the Dissemination and Communication by providing guidance and carrying out several implementation aspects. In addition, all HYPERION partners will be deeply involved in the Dissemination and Communication work, providing contents, developing scientific publications, participating in high-impact events, promoting the project's outcomes, etc.

1.1 Purpose of the document

The objective of HYPERION CDP is to identify and organize the activities to be performed in order to communicate the benefits of an **integrated resilience assessment platform**, addressing multi-hazard risk understanding, better preparedness, faster, adapted and efficient response, and **sustainable reconstruction** of historic areas; to disseminate results of HYPERION project; and to raise citizens awareness and policy makers implication.

The present document constitutes Deliverable D9.3 (CDP, Communication and Dissemination Plan) in the framework of WP9 (Dissemination, Communication and Standardization Activities), regarding **Task 9.2 (Development and update of a Dissemination and Communication Plan)**.

The main purpose of this document is to develop a comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy for the HYPERION project that will act as a general roadmap for all HYPERION-related communication and dissemination activities. It aims to serve as the project's integrated approach for informing and creating awareness about its assets, engaging society in its evolutions and impact and efficiently publishing project's results.

It summarizes the strategy of the consortium and concrete actions to disseminate the foreground generated by the project, pointing out responsibilities and activities. In the CDP the type of messages, key audiences and channels are specified and detailed. The CDP also includes a project visual identity and common layout for the communication materials. Dissemination is a horizontal activity and concentrates on disseminating the results of HYPERION project itself to a wide range of existing and/or potential stakeholders. The practical experience and guidance that will emerge from the project work, will be of relevance to an array of stakeholders within EU and beyond and will be of value across different sectors and internationally.

To fulfil these aims, HYPERION will work through various carefully focused groups and committees through formal and informal mechanisms. Clear channels of communications between the project partners themselves as well as with a broader community will play a crucial role in the success of the project.

1.2 Intended Readership

This Deliverable is "Public", thus accessible to anyone interested.

It is primarily written for the European Commission (EC) Project Officer (PO) and the consortium members of the HYPERION Project in order to inform them about the HYPERION brand identity and dedicated guidelines, the project's communication and dissemination materials and channels as well as the planned activities. More specifically, it serves as an instrument that helps them understand the communication's objectives of the project and how these could contribute to project's awareness in an efficient and effective way.

Nevertheless, special effort and attention has been given in making this report as a stand-alone document and comprehensible for the general public.

1.3 Key Concepts defined

As communication and dissemination are the key concepts in this deliverable, here below we have included their definition and an explanation of their relationship.

Dissemination is the public disclosure of the results of the project in any medium. It is a process of promotion and awareness-raising right from the beginning of a project. It makes research results known to various stakeholder groups (like research peers, industry and other commercial actors, professional organisations, policymakers) in a targeted way, to enable them to use the results in their own work. This process must be planned and organised at the beginning of each project, usually in a dissemination plan. (“What is the difference between dissemination, exploitation and communication?” Research and Innovation Participant portal, FAQ ID: 933, March 2016)

Communication means taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, and possibly engaging them in a two-way exchange. The aim is to reach out to society as a whole and in particular to some specific audiences while demonstrating how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges. (“What is the difference between dissemination, exploitation and communication?” Research and Innovation Participant portal, FAQ ID: 933, March 2016)

Starting with **Communication**, this CDP differentiates between various kinds of communicating and networking actions depending on the nature of the content to transmit, which audiences are being addressed and what kind of interaction is deemed necessary to ensure the impact of the project. In that respect, there are two communication pillars that HYPERION CDP focuses on:

- internal communication,
- external communication and stakeholders’ engagement and networking.

Internal communication applies to the exchange of information and communication within the project - among project partners, while **external communication** refers to the activities, focused on reaching out the various targeted audiences that the project is addressing. Furthermore, **stakeholders’ engagement and networking** are about including a targeted community into a corresponding discussion about:

- the role of HYPERION, its concept, purposes and achievement processes and
- the capacities, future enhancements and possible drivers that may lead to address multi-hazard risk understanding, better preparedness, faster, adapted and efficient response, and sustainable reconstruction of historic areas.

This includes events, where exchange of positions, views and information can be facilitated, and consultation processes intended at obtaining targeted feedback.

2. INTERNAL COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

2.1 Communication Approach

The significance of **internal communication** lies in its relation to the external communication and dissemination of project's assets. The strategy analysed in the following pages, aims to foster cooperation and knowledge exchange among all project partners. HYPERION's internal communication channels and activities have been chosen and are implemented to serve as a tool for an effective external communication and will support the efficient delivery of messages to the identified key audiences.

2.1.1 Internal Communication Activities

HYPERION partners will be engaged with each other by immediate distribution and exchange of information on the collaborative system (REDMINE) set up for this purpose, through online messaging across the partnership and, when necessary, through targeted messaging to subgroups within the partnership. To facilitate this exchange of information each partner will designate, apart from its legal and project representatives, a contact person for each task it is involved with.

Internal communication, when referring to messages and news (whatever nature they have; announcements, presentations, etc.) that are to be published for informing the general public (including targeted audiences), serves to facilitate efficient and effective external communication. To that end, HYPERION WP Leaders and the Project Coordinator, will be tasked with regularly compiling and identifying the relevant information that WP9 Leader needs to transmit and communicate externally.

The Information flow within HYPERION will be ensured by the exchange of internal technical and business documents, the notification of relevant new publications in the literature, or by the standard bodies and the reports from external meetings.

All documentation will be exchanged based on a set of guidelines that are agreed and described in the GA. A web project document repository (REDMINE) is available by ICCS from the very beginning of the project. Telephone and fax will be used for urgent needs only. Urgent correspondence over e-mail will be sent with a request for explicit acknowledge. Ordinary mail will be used for strictly formal correspondence, i.e. when executive signatures are required. Adherence to the agreed communications standards will be enforced by the PC and the QM. The Project Coordination Team (PCT) will meet every four to six months to monitor project progress. WP meetings will also be around every four months, most of the times combined with PCT meetings or organized workshops (either in WP2 or the exploitation workshops). WP meetings may take place whenever required through telco. All meeting arrangements initiated by partner will be communicated to the PCT in advance, which will undertake to organise the timing and location of meetings, by combining more than one meeting in parallel, thus minimizing travel costs.

Additionally, the other eight WP Leaders (WP1-WP8 & WP10) will be engaged in informing IEMC and ICCS on the progress made in their respective work packages at any time when this is considered relevant for enhancing the external profile HYPERION so that all outputs and newsworthy events can be communicated promptly and regularly. If necessary, WP Leaders, other than of WP9, will appoint a contact person to act as contact and rapporteur towards the WP9 Leader regarding their communication activities.

2.2 Internal Communication Tools

Several mechanisms and means are to be implemented (under the responsibility of WP9 Leader) to enable an effective use of internal communication channels.

2.2.1 Working platform

www.redmine.org has been selected as the supporting project management platform. This choice was made because the same platform was used by most of the partners in previous projects. Corresponding user privileges and online profiles have been given to all partners. This platform gathers the internal communication processes, including message exchanges, upload of documentation, deadlines establishment, milestones fixing, and internal assignment of tasks and duties. Establishing this Internal Communication Platform is responsibility of the Partner ICCS. Adequate online messaging services (on individual or group basis) included in the platform are used by involved participants. Those lists are updated regularly. The lists differentiate between project members and their roles, so that messages can be sent automatically to groups, such as Work Package Leaders, Task Leaders, and Finance Administrators, Project Managers, etc. The lists were created as early as in M1, and are either

- of general purpose, or
- at group level (Work Package and/or coordination and/or others as agreed during the project).

The first one, namely the general HYPERION mailing list, is in place since the starting of the project.

2.2.2 HYPERION website

<https://www.hyperion-project.eu/> HYPERION's website serves as a powerful communication tool and a key element of engagement with the partners. The progress of the project is visualized on the HYPERION website. Its basic objective is to create an easily accessible public platform for dissemination of public deliverables, open access publications, presentations, newsletter issues etc. Moreover, it acts as a repository for materials for them that may be required at disparate locations.

In addition, a GitHub³ open software development site will be created or the ICCS GitLab repository will be used to attract research community participation and long-term engagement in the creation of the SG simulator interfaces, the MHVAT toolkit and the HRAP engine.

2.2.3 Partner progress meetings

Regarding more direct exchanges, to facilitate inter-project communications and encourage the exchange of information relevant for the communication project leader, ICCS set up the Kick-off meeting in Athens, Greece on the 4th of June 2019. It has been agreed to organise monthly teleconferences of the Project WP. The Project Coordination Team (PCT) will meet every four to six months to monitor project progress.

2.2.4 All-hands meetings

HYPERION project will hold All-Hands meetings when there is an occasion and mainly, while project outputs are prepared in intense collaboration and open discussion, these meetings will be instrumental in intensifying internal communication also beyond the open event.

2.3` HYPERION identity/logo design

The logo of HYPERION and the full graphic identity linked to the project (a visual charter including different formats, colour scheme, typography etc.) have been developed in wide consultation across the project. The design plot of the logo allows the partners to use it in every communication activity, both internal and external.

2.3.1 HYPERION templates

In the context of HYPERION's consistent brand identity and in order to keep a credible and professional "look and feel", a set of HYPERION templates (letters, posters, power point presentations, deliverables, minutes, business cards) have been created based on the project's brand guidelines and are available to all partners through HYPERION's common online collaborative tool.

2.3.2 HYPERION internal communication and dissemination procedures

For better updating, collecting and reporting of all upcoming HYPERION's dissemination activities, an internal mechanism has been created, called dissemination procedures, to monitor all such activities. The basic objectives of these procedures are:

- ✓ To produce high quality HYPERION publications and presentations;

³ GitHub software development platform: <https://github.com/>

- ✓ To avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information;
- ✓ To monitor and keep an appropriate registry of the dissemination activities of the project.

All these procedures are described in detail in Annex 1 of this document.

2.3.3 Repository for HYPERION events and journals

In the context of HYPERION, special attention is given to the project's dissemination activities as well as in the event organisation and participation, throughout the course of the project.

IEMC, being the WP Leader, with the creation of a repository for HYPERION events and journals that are considered as valuable opportunities for the project. The repository includes an indicative list of proposed scientific journals and an indicative list of proposed upcoming European and international events and it is regularly updated mainly by IEMC and by the consortium partners. In addition, HYPERION partners are regularly informed through emails about upcoming key opportunities so they will be able to benefit from them.

This repository is described in detail in Chapter 3 of this document.

3. External communication and stakeholders' engagement and networking

3.1 Objectives

The Communication and Dissemination Strategy of HYPERION aims to develop an infrastructure which will foster cooperation and knowledge exchange between different research communities in order to enhance resilience and reduce vulnerability of historic areas to climate change and other natural hazards, also accounting for their synergistic impact; and improve reconstruction and economic and social recovery of historic areas by local authorities and communities through the use of new knowledge and tools.

The aim of HYPERION Communication activities is to effectively disseminate information of the activities of the project and to communicate its outcomes to multiple audiences. The objectives of the DCP are the following:

- To develop an effective dissemination and communication strategy;
- To communicate and disseminate project results and products/systems during and after the lifetime of the project;
- To promote project technologies;
- To ensure widespread use and awareness raising of the developed project technologies;
- To identify the main stakeholder types/categories with emphasis to identify and prioritize dissemination tools;

- To specify how the stakeholders can be activated to contribute to the project.

3.2 Communication Approach

The general purpose of HYPERION's Communication and Dissemination Strategy is to develop effective and efficient communication and dissemination ideas, ensuring that it will abide to the core objectives of the agreed dissemination strategy and that key messages are properly and consistently delivered.

The Communication and Dissemination Strategy of the HYPERION project is based on a four-step approach, as outlined here below:

- **Stage 1 (M1-M12):** Raising awareness of project activities, outputs and benefits through diverse channels to audiences that do not require a detailed technical knowledge of the work carried out.
- **Stage 2 (M6-M24):** Promoting a deeper understanding of new knowledge and results for several audiences who can benefit from what the project can offer.
- **Stage 3 (M18-M30):** Engaging with target groups to encourage their willingness to make use of project results. This stage will be the main focus of WP7&8;
- **Stage 4 (M24-M42):** Influencing decision-making within organisations regarding the uptake of HYPERION outputs and supporting the implementation of the Exploitation Plan. This stage will be the focus of the final WP (WP10).

3.3 D&C SWOT Analysis

The way in which the HYPERION was introduced on behalf of the consortium, as well as the context in which the project is being implemented, leads to several unique strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats regarding its communication and dissemination objectives.

The strengths of the project are articulated in the large network of partners, involved in existing research (infra)structures with their communication channels, rather than the existence of representatives from each target audience within the consortium, the projects long term vision, as well as the digitization of analogue resources in a transdisciplinary framework, which promotes a use of the 'state-of-the-art' standardization-tools.

The weaknesses, such as the difficulty of tailoring messages to specific target groups in order to reach audiences beyond academia and the downsides of putting too much weight on technological aspects in communication activities should likewise be considered.

On the other hand, HYPERION offers opportunities to support public bodies and/or CH resilience projects, through linking Outputs to a globally rolled out, validated, open data source, which might tackle down real necessities of upgrading existing services to meet the EC standards, as well as the worldwide trends in the specific domain.

Identified threats manifest themselves in the targeted audiences not being familiar with terminologies and concepts about micro-climatic and atmospheric stressors, consequently missing out communication and participation approaches specifically addressed to them after losing interest in the project rather than not being aware of the project's existence. Stakeholders from social sciences and humanities, archaeologists, archaeometrists to architects, conservators to CH experts and governmental bodies might struggle with breaking down established, existing (traditional) practices and standards, whilst other observers might show unwillingness to make their data available under open access. Another threat-issue is addressed in missing (new) output and outcomes due to a non-efficient collaboration with HYPERION partners, while they themselves might fail to support the infrastructure's sustainability, by limiting themselves to contributing input but not providing information and tutorials regarding the platforms usability. Therefore, a non-efficient use of the infrastructure due to a lack of information on how to use it should be considered.

The Table below visualizes the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats described above:

Table 1: D&C SWOT Analysis

Strengths		Weaknesses	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HYPERION has included major players, including worldwide end-users, industrial partners and academia partners: each one is expert in the relevant field of CH • most partners are involved in existing research structures with multiple communication channels • representatives from each stakeholder group and user community are present in the consortium • project's long-term vision • transdisciplinary – linking different research fields • partners actively involved in using and promoting state-of-the-art existing systems and facilities. • Open-source nature of flagship HRAP platform will help develop trust in the methodology and encourage scientific community engagement. The availability of a dual (non-GPL) license will also allow industry to participate and employ HRAP for commercial products. • Regularly evaluation of dissemination goals • Information accessible through web-based tools 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CH and cities as end-users (operators) are often not particularly interested in sophisticated (ICT-based) solutions, especially given the current level of economic crisis (particularly in the South and South /East Europe) • Need special training of the system operators • Difficulties among different communities in HYPERION multidisciplinary approach • tailoring messages to diverse audiences/target groups may be difficult • difficulty reaching audiences beyond academia • Sceptical attitude on the use of new communication/ dissemination tools (e.g. REDMINE / social media) • Lack of direct citizen involvement 	
	S	W	
	O	T	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking with other projects • Real necessity of upgrading existing services to meet the EC standards, as well as the worldwide trends in the specific domain • support policy making and projects by engagement and support • project's output may be rolled out beyond European borders • Increasing the availability of validated open data 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data sharing and • Heterogeneous legislation/policies per country / type of organistaion • Competition for low cost CH-oriented management (inspection/maintenance) tools • target audience not familiar with project's terminology and concepts 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of different D&C tools (traditional and new) • Exchange good practises with partners and stakeholders <p>Opportunities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • missing output due to non-efficient collaboration with partners • difficulties with breaking down existing (traditional) practice of established professionals and policy makers • unwillingness to make data available under open access • non-efficient use of infrastructure due to lack of knowledge of how-to-use • Risks of social media use (e.g. social media bots, internet trolls, Information leakage) <p>Threats</p>
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3.4 Target Audiences

In order to secure success in engaging stakeholders in using HYPERION results, the focus of the project’s dissemination and communication efforts targets large historic areas with climate data value chains. Stakeholder engagement is the key to the success of any dissemination initiative, and stakeholder identification is the first and foremost important task in effective stakeholder engagement. One of the main tasks of HYPERION is thus to define target audiences according to their interests, needs and drivers. In order to achieve effective dissemination, it is necessary to understand stakeholder motivations. This will enable the Consortium to effectively engage, communicate with and promote future dialogue between different stakeholders.

The target audiences for HYPERION project dissemination have been grouped into five different categories, namely the scientific community, private sector, policy makers, public bodies and general public.

Scientific Community	Private Sector	Public Bodies	Policy Makers	General Public
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Academia •Researchers •Applied Technology •Field Test Facilities •Other H2020 And FP7 Related Projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Technology Developers •Supply/ Service Chain •Utilities •Archaeologists •Archaeometrists •Architects •Conservators To CH Experts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Local Government •Cultural Authorities From The Ministries •Governmental Bodies Dealing With Planning, Policies And Socio-economics •Environmental Policy Bodies •European Commission 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Environmental Planning •Regulators •Permitting Bodies •Antiquities Planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Environmental And Cultural Ngos •Other Users Of The CH •Citizen Organisations •Individual Citizens •Students

Figure 1: Target audiences for HYPERION project dissemination

3.5 Project's Communication Channels

For an effective messaging, a broad range of communication channels including traditional and new media will be utilized by the project to reach, speak and interact with its target audiences, capturing their attention frequently and precisely.

The main communication and dissemination channels used to target specific groups of stakeholders have been divided into one-way channels and two-way channels. One-way channels have the benefit of achieving broad visibility, reaching the general public “en masse” and enjoying the credibility of established media platforms. Two-way channels can be seen as more effective as they involve dialogue, interactivity and flexibility, but they often reach a smaller number of people. The key communication channels for HYPERION are detailed below.

One-way Communication Channels

- Project website
- Digital media, such as online newspapers and magazines
- Traditional media, such as TV, radio and press
- Communication and dissemination materials, such as roll up banners, leaflets, posters, Short Animated Videos, etc.
- Newsletters
- Annual magazines
- Press releases, Advertorials
- Publications in scientific journals

Two-way Communication Channels

- Social media: Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook
- Interactive discussion on social media, social media campaigns
- Dialogue with networks, communities and associations
- Physical meetings
- Field events such as conferences, fairs, special sessions and workshops
- Pilots
- Final Event

Figure 2: HYPERION's Communication Channels

Moreover, each project partner is committed to create a high level of publicity for the project right from the beginning, the launch and objectives of HYPERION are communicated through partners organisations communication channels to generate broad public awareness of HYPERION activities.

3.5.1 One-way Communication Channels

Project website

The HYPERION website (<https://www.hyperion-project.eu/>) will be the main interface for communication to the public. Analysis of it is provided in deliverable 9.2. The Website contains information on the project’s goals, the partnership, the proposed activities and the foreseen/achieved results. It will also allow having access to the dissemination material and will host a blog to facilitate the interaction between partners and interested parties. In order to maximize its visibility, free or affordable methods to increase page ranking on search engines will be used.

Its basic objective is to create an easily accessible public platform for dissemination of deliverables, open access publications, presentations, newsletter issues etc. Interactivity and updated content will attract attention and repeated visits. The web will include information of the project and the possibility to contact with project partners for interested stakeholders. Interested parties will be able to register to receive updated information and networking opportunities. Electronic newsletters reporting on project events results will be published on the website of the project reaching a wide community of potential stakeholders.

The website is the main visual window for communicating the material of the project and it was available at month five (5) from the project kick off meeting in Athens. You can access it from the URL: <https://www.hyperion-project.eu/>

The website follows the visual identity of HYPERION, as used in all project communication materials. This allows us to vamp up the visual and be more interactive with everyone involved.

Figure 3: HYPERION’s Website view

The website provides all relevant information about HYPERION. It is divided in 8 parts as follows:

- ✓ ABOUT: The sub-topics included in this section are: Hyperion Vision, The concept, Objectives, To whom it may concern, impact and innovation potential are on display in this section.
- ✓ PARTNERS: Contains the information about the partners as well as the link to their own sites.
- ✓ TEST SITES: Information and visual material for all four different sites are included in this section.
- ✓ RESULTS TO DATE: Deliverables, Publications and presentations are included in this section. All existing results are uploaded, following all the steps which are included in the procedures. This is a downloadable area where every individual can find in depth information about the project.
- ✓ NEWSROOM: News, Newsletter, Magazines, in the Media and the Media Kit, are included in this section. As “News” are included in this section, being the attracting part of newsroom, it will constantly be updated with information about the project activities and results throughout the entire lifetime of the project.
- ✓ GET INVOLVED: In this section the visitor can register for the newsletters. Via this section of the webpage, links to the official Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn accounts of the project – the main social media tools used for HYPERION is provided. The visual identity has been taken into account while creating these channels.
- ✓ LIAISONS: HYPERION will collaborate with European Research and Technological Development initiatives, participating in important working groups and events. Networking, co-organising sessions in EU conferences and preparation of joint dissemination activities, will be included in this section. Three main projects are briefly mentioned in this section.
- ✓ CONTACT US: Direct contact to the main persons involved in the project (the project coordinator, the project manager and the webmaster). Using the e-mailing option the visitor can directly communicate with the persons mentioned.

Cookies policy

The website follows the Commission's guidelines on privacy and data protection and inform users that cookies are not being used to gather information unnecessarily. The ePrivacy directive – more specifically Article 5(3) – requires prior informed consent for storage or for access to information stored on a user's terminal equipment.

Web Site Maintenance

Development, maintenance and content creation for HYPERION website is done by IEMC. This includes uploading of the public deliverables as well as announcements of information and events to be displayed at the site. The news and events section at the site will include HYPERION related stuff as well as related European news and events (updated by HYPERION team with assistance from IEMC and other partners when

relevant). Below is shown the minimum project targets for the website. Website statistics is provided through Google Analytics (i.e. number of sessions, unique visitors, number of pages visited, time etc.).

Table 2: Website targets

Medium	Target Group	Geographical Outreach	Success - Impact
Project website	All	International	1,000/year

Press Releases and Media Coverage

Gaining positive and consistent coverage in the media is expected to have an incredible impact on the work we do. Getting more people thinking positively about the project and spreading its messages across to a wider audience are key prerequisites for HYPERION’s communication and dissemination activities and a great way of providing the project and its assets with greater credibility.

Project’s press releases will be developed by IEMC for all major events and in order to disseminate the project’s key findings and results in various trusted local and European media. Partners will be responsible for translations and regional adaptations as well as to create media contact lists with key journalists and bloggers specialised in culture, technology and science.

The consortium, always in close collaboration with the EC staff, will also disseminate the project vision and main results through various means offered by the EU, e.g., Horizon Magazine, research*EU results magazine, EuroNews TV etc. Partners will also investigate possibilities to participate in EU research conferences and public events, e.g., EU City Forum (2019), Open Door Days and H2020 Researchers Nights events.

Concerning European Commission dissemination network, HYPERION will be disseminated in:

- CORDIS’ “projects and results” service that provides: (i) “project information” based on the project’s grant agreement, (ii) “report summaries” that come from the publishable summaries of periodic and final reports submitted by the project participants and approved by the project officer and (iii) “results in brief” written by CORDIS science editors based on each report summary,
- CORDIS Wire, to publish articles on the CORDIS News and Events service,
- research*eu results magazine, that features highlights from the most exciting EU-funded research and development projects.

Table 3: Dissemination targets

Medium	Target Group	Geographical Outreach	Success - Impact
Press releases to newspapers/ magazines (online & print)	All	Local/National	40
Presentations of project results in media offered by EU	All	European	4
TV / radio presentation	All	Local/National	9 (one per country)

Notice: For Press releases in external means, i.e. not directly linked to any HYPERION partner: newspapers or magazines, scientific journals, websites, etc.

Every partner must register the following information:

- Order
- Date
- Media name
- Media type: Newspaper, Magazine, Journal, Website, others.
- Media scope: Local, Regional, National, European, International.
- Media language
- Potential outreach: number of subscribers, followers, readers, etc.
- Title: Headline of the information
- Author: Journalist, institution, etc.
- Type: Printed, online, both.
- Description: Short comment on the contents
- Length: Number of words, pages, etc.
- Additional comments
- Link: webpage, if available

Communication and dissemination material

The visual identity (logo and style) of the project will help external audience to easily identify HYPERION and contribute to the project visibility by providing a clear identity from the launching of the project. All the communication and dissemination tools (project website, Research Gate, Twitter, LinkedIn page & Facebook), materials (leaflets, presentations, posters, etc.) and deliverables will employ the visual identity developed for the project, guaranteeing a professional and consistent look.

The communication materials that will be produced are:

- ✓ *A Project leaflet*, to provide our audiences with an attractive and written project overview and summary of the main project objectives and results.
- ✓ *A Factsheet* that will be able to be distributed in printed form (handed out at conferences or other events) or in electronic version (PDF file) and will be also downloadable from the project website.
- ✓ *Rollup Banners and Posters* to display the project’s visual identity and providing a particularly practical tool with which to promote HYPERION and deliver its assets, drawing the attention of the audiences during the different events.
- ✓ *A Project General Presentation*, describing the objectives and the main achieved results for presenting the project in different forums, such as internal presentations inside of the partners, presentations at schools/universities, visits with clients, etc. These presentations will be downloadable from the website and could be *uploaded in SlideShare*.
- ✓ *A Project related video*, to communicate the project’s vision, objectives and results. This will be accessible from the website and could be uploaded in YouTube.

Newsletters

We will publish **2 newsletters per year** to raise awareness of the HYPERION project and communicate its outcomes and learnings.

HYPERION’s newsletter will be disseminated via project’s website, social media and direct mailing to a dedicated list of recipients that is currently being enriched via a dedicated subscription form uploaded on HYPERION’s website.

Moreover, partner recipients of the newsletter will be encouraged to spread HYPERION newsletter to their own networks, which is expected to gradually result in a substantial number of subscribers and to generate word-of-mouth referrals.

The content of each newsletter will be agreed collaboratively between the WP leader, the Coordinator and the team in charge of writing the corresponding issue.

Experts and professionals from different fields (science, cultural heritage, etc.) who can contribute to raise awareness on HYPERION will be invited to contribute to the newsletters.

KPI/ Success Impact	At least 2 newsletters per year
---------------------	---------------------------------

The structure of the newsletters is presented on the table below. Each partner is asked to send the draft of the newsletter to the Coordinator one week before the launching date. All newsletters will be available on HYPERION website.

Each newsletter will be built according to the following structure:
HYPERION Logo on the top of the page, centered.

Calendar/next events (e.g. participatory activities) – 1/4 page

Topic creation. Something out of the mainstream if possible.

Theory facts, approaches, documents that help to reinforce the understanding of the project.

Footer which contains all the projects social media accounts and contact emails

Image display Partners responsible for drafting the newsletter will also be asked to add 2 or 3 (high quality) pictures to illustrate the newsletter (e.g. one of the interviewee, one or two of activities as examples of good practices). They will provide team member's contact details in order to be integrated in the mailing list.

When available, they should also provide persons' Twitter account to be mentioned in the project's posts thus multiplying opportunities to reach out. Tweet and share.

For example: @personsname was invited by @Hyperion to speak about in @hyperion newsletter + link to read the newsletter.

Annual magazines

An annual magazine providing valuable information on HYPERION's developments, key findings, forthcoming events and other important news in the fields related to the project will be prepared and distributed to various contacts once a year, starting from M12.

HYPERION's annual magazine will be disseminated via project's website, social media and direct mailing to a dedicated list of recipients that is currently being enriched via a dedicated subscription form uploaded on HYPERION's website. The main objective is to increase awareness and understanding of HYPERION's assets and fields of relevance, build new relationships as well as maintain regular contact with HYPERION's key target audiences.

Publications in scientific journals

Scientific publications are an effective way to disseminate high-level project information and to attract the interest of representatives of various target groups. The research partners will preferably publish the results in indexed peer-reviewed journals, which are addressed to academic staff as well as experts/ professionals. Research partners within the consortium when appropriate, will present HYPERION in scientific journals or magazines of sectors and industries related to the project outcomes, always taking into account confidentiality and IPR protection aspects.

Work will be made to publish papers in well-respected and highly rated peer-reviewed journals. This task will be carried out mostly by the research partners, and the publications will cover several project fields of work. Effort will be made to secure Open Access (OA) to all interested persons, mainly through the project website but also through respective OA repositories such as OpenAIRE.

The publication of materials by the project includes:

- ✓ scientific publications in academic journals;

- ✓ training materials;
- ✓ service specific brochures and fact sheets;
- ✓ project brochures and leaflets.

HYPERION team will establish an editorial committee for project publications such as reports, training materials and other literature.

The membership of the committee will be convened from the project partnership or external experts as appropriate to the publication. Material published by the project will be made available under a Creative Commons Attribution, Share-Alike, Non-Commercial (CC BY-SA) license.

Publications will be available for download from the web site with printed materials being produced for distribution at events, etc.

Scientific publications by partners concerning project work in academic journals are strongly encouraged. Standard academic good practice concerning citation of authors is anticipated with the proviso that authors should:

- a) mention EU support for the work;
- b) notify the consortium of the publication;
- c) provide a digital copy to the consortium, to be made available on the website (if the publisher agrees) or a link provided to an archive copy elsewhere; or to be kept in storage, if self-archiving is not allowed.

Medium	Target Group	Geographical Outreach	Success - Impact
Publications in scientific journals	Academic	International	At least 2 publications in scientific ISI journals

Suggested journals for potential publications

IEMC, as WP Leader, has proceeded, with the creation of a repository for HYPERION events and journals that are considered as valuable opportunities for the project. The repository includes an indicative list of proposed scientific journals and an indicative list of proposed upcoming European and international events and it is regularly updated mainly by WP Leader and by the consortium partners. In addition, HYPERION partners are regularly informed through emails about upcoming key opportunities so they will be able to benefit from them.

Table 4: List of scientific journals

Journal	Description	Frequency
APT BULLETIN: JOURNAL OF PRESERVATION TECHNOLOGY	The Association for Preservation Technology is directly involved in the application of methods and materials to maintain, conserve, and protect historic structures and sites for future use and appreciation.	Three issues per year
Building and Environment	Building and Environment is an international journal that publishes original research papers and review articles related to building science, urban physics, and human interaction with the indoor and outdoor built environment	Monthly
Construction and Building materials	An international journal dedicated to the investigation and innovative use of materials in construction and repair. Construction and Building Materials provides an international forum for the dissemination of innovative and original research and development in the field of construction and building materials.	36 issues per year
Digital Applications in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage (DAACH)	DAACH is an on-line, peer-reviewed journal in which scholars can publish 3D digital models of the world's cultural heritage sites, monuments, and palaeoanthropological remains accompanied by associated academic articles.	Quarterly
Global Environmental Change	Global Environmental Change is a peer-reviewed international journal publishing high quality, theoretically and empirically rigorous articles, which advance knowledge about the human and policy dimensions of global environmental change. The journal interprets global environmental change to mean the outcome of processes that are manifest in localities, but with consequences at multiple spatial, temporal and socio-political scales.	Six issues per year
Heritage Science	Heritage Science is an open access journal publishing original peer-reviewed research covering scientific, mathematical and computational methods and analysis of objects, materials, artefacts and artworks of cultural and historical significance in the context of heritage and conservation studies.	Annually
International Journal of Architectural Heritage(IJAH)	IJAH provides a multidisciplinary scientific overview of existing resources and modern technologies useful for the study and repair of historical buildings and other structures. The journal will include information on history, methodology, materials,	10 issues per year

	survey, inspection, non-destructive testing, analysis, diagnosis, remedial measures, and strengthening techniques.	
International Journal of Heritage in Digital Era(IJHDE)	IJHDE is a quarterly high-quality peer reviewed journal in the area of Digital Cultural Heritage and Digital Libraries. http://www.multi-science.co.uk/ijhde.htm	Quarterly
International Journal of Research & Development (IJRD)	This journal is dedicated to increasing the depth of knowledge with the ultimate aim of improving research. The Journal invites original, Unpublished research, review papers in inter-disciplinary areas.	Monthly
International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management	Open Access Journal by Emerald Publishing The journal publishes papers dealing with policy-making on climate change, and methodological approaches to cope with the problems deriving from climate change. It disseminates experiences from projects and case studies where due consideration to environmental, economic, social and political aspects is given and especially the links and leverages that can be attained by this holistic approach.	5 issues per year
International Journal of Conservation Science (IJCS)	IJCS is a high-quality peer-reviewed journal devoted to the publication of original research papers in applied conservation science and its broad range of applications. IJCS it is an open access journal. IJCS publishes original research papers, review articles, book and project reviews in all areas dedicated to applied conservation of natural and cultural heritage and other related areas of environmental science and engineering.	Quarterly
Journal of Cultural Heritage (JCH)	JCH is a multidisciplinary journal of science and technology for studying problems concerning conservation and awareness of cultural heritage in a wide framework. The main purpose of JCH is to publish original papers which comprise previously unpublished data and present innovative methods concerning all scientific aspects related to the knowledge of cultural heritage as well as novel interpretation and theoretical issues related to preservation.	Six issues per year
Journal of Cultural Heritage Management and Sustainable	JCHMSD publishes a range of theoretical and practical papers based upon quantitative and qualitative methodological approaches. Articles are particularly welcome on immovable cultural heritage	Quarterly

Development (JCHMSD)	and its role in sustainable development, as well as the sustainable development of immovable cultural heritage. Immovable cultural heritage ranges from cultural landscapes to monuments. Other relevant dimensions of cultural heritage will also be considered for publication e.g. rural cultural heritage, indigenous cultural heritage management.	
Quantum Journal of environmental Studies (QJOES)	QJOES is an international journal for the publication of important, very high quality, research relating to environmental science and environmental management. https://www.qjoes.com/ .	Semi Annually

3.5.2 Two-way Communication Channels

Social media: Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook

In order to consistently and effectively communicate with HYPERION's multiple, often diverse targeted audiences, and create social links with them, succeeding wide awareness on project's activities and developments, dedicated HYPERION social media accounts have been created and linked to HYPERION's website.

HYPERION's consortium has decided to focus on the following selected Social Media:

- ✓ A Facebook account (<https://www.facebook.com/HyperionEUProject/>) that is considered by far the most popular social media channel in HYPERION consortium's countries;
- ✓ A Twitter account (<https://twitter.com/EuHyperion>) will be used as a direct communication instrument for reaching the general public and following Horizon 2020 communication and dissemination campaigns launched by the European Commission. The social media platforms the Commission and its agencies use will be employed to expand project audience, which will be accomplished by adding #H2020 and tagging @EU_H2020 to HYPERION tweets.
- ✓ A LinkedIn account (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/hyperioneuproject>) page will be used for reaching stakeholders and industry professionals. Official LinkedIn groups will be joined to raise awareness among the different project topics professionals and industry.

The HYPERION website will have direct access to these social networks by clicking over the icons situated on a visible part of the website. In this way, it will be easy for every user to participate in this when the website is visited.

Social Media Strategy

The social media strategy aims at:

- Identifying and approaching persons and organizations already active in fields related to the project activities (e.g. professionals in LinkedIn);
- Get project/ service well known through social media and call for “Action”;
- Spreading news/content about the project: project content, activities, news, results etc.;
- Engaging social media followers, preferably by directing them to HYPERION website;
- Creating interactive forums at European and national scale (external stakeholders).

Actions to be performed in this context include:

- Identifying and approaching the relevant persons and organizations;
- Get enlisted in relevant LinkedIn Professional Groups;
- Regular social media posts (e.g. 1 per week in each media) aiming at informing or initiating discussions/debates/feedback;
- Social Media Campaigns: Boosting posts towards the target group;
- Establishing national social media accounts as appropriate or using already existing accounts with relevant followers/members;

HYPERION uses the three most popular social networks: **Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn**. Facebook is the most popular social network in terms of unique monthly visitors, followed by Twitter and LinkedIn. Facebook is a social network that allows users to interact with others, and share photos, video, and information about the ongoing activities of the program. LinkedIn has a more professional profile than the other two and it is initially centred around careers. It enables users to connect and share content with other professionals, including colleagues. As such, LinkedIn Groups provide a place for professionals in the same industry or with similar interests to share content, find answers, make business contacts, and establish themselves as experts. LinkedIn, the world's largest professional networking platform, is used to expand our network and create more work opportunities by joining groups and discussions on various topics that we are interested in.

Twitter which is what’s happening in the world and what people are talking about right now. Mainly used to post the activities that are being carried out as well as to cover the PM meetings.

Measures to grow Social Media Accounts

The strategy for this is as follows:

- First step is to map individual personal contacts as well as organisations with a potential interest in the project (European sites: EC Network);
- Secondly to invite these contacts to connect with the project either through the social medias or through personal messages. This will include the stakeholders involved in the project and press distribution lists;
- Followers can also be reached through so called adds (paid advertisement), which can be targeted specifically at potential followers (geographically, age, sex, interests);
- To maintain the audience and keeping accounts interactive, it is important to qualify and optimize the discussions and information provided and do regularly

postings. For this purpose, responsibilities have been distributed on discussions, posts, articles, etc. and particularly as regards the LinkedIn account.

Postings - keeping the social media working and interactive

The regular posts will aim at:

- ✓ Promoting the website and the Database;
- ✓ Linking with contents at the website: articles, new content, events etc.;
- ✓ Reporting from project events (consortium meetings, workshops etc. – with photos and comments);
- ✓ Informing on important progress / results / success stories of the Project (i.e. the Database, Sustainable Energy Planning Concept etc.);
- ✓ Promoting public project publications;
- ✓ Reporting on participation in EU events & congresses and any other media activities of the project (radio broadcasts, TV broadcasts, etc.);
- ✓ Informing of any partnership of the project;
- ✓ Sharing information on other associated events (EU, other projects etc.);
- ✓ Sharing relevant contents from other sites (projects, EU organisations, local organisations, initiatives etc.);
- ✓ Linking to interesting articles related to the project theme, etc. and beginning a thread/conversation with the social media connections (sharing/retweeting);
- ✓ LinkedIn particularly: Professional articles from the academic partners.
- ✓

Social Media Accounts Indicators

According to the DoA the following indicator should be reached:

Table 5: Social media indicators

Medium	Target Group	Geographical Outreach	Success – Impact
LinkedIn	All	International	200 members
Twitter	All	International	200 members
All social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn)	All	International	150 posts/year

Statistics will be collected from all social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn) and will count followers, members, outreach of posts (e.g. number of persons reached), video plays etc.

Overview of Social Media Accounts

As for local dissemination through social media it has been decided to use existing social media accounts hosted by the project partners in those cases where new accounts are estimated to be not effective, as use of existing accounts with many followers will secure a higher outreach. The table below indicates current social media accounts created within the project and indicative local social media accounts that can be used to promote the project.

Table 6: Social media accounts for program promotion

Type	Country	Host	Link	Followers
LinkedIn	EU	HYPERION	https://www.linkedin.com/company/hyperioneuproject/?viewAsMember=true	16
Twitter	EU	HYPERION	https://twitter.com/EuHyperion	139
Facebook	EU	HYPERION	https://www.facebook.com/HyperionEUProject/	93
Facebook	Greece	AUTH	https://www.linkedin.com/school/aristotle-university-of-thessaloniki-auth-/	70,654
Twitter	Greece	AUTH	https://twitter.com/Aristoteleio	7,136
LinkedIn	Greece	AUTH	https://www.linkedin.com/school/aristotle-university-of-thessaloniki-auth-/	
Twitter	Finland	FMI	https://twitter.com/meteorologit	164.1K
Facebook	Finland	FMI	https://www.facebook.com/fmibeta/	3.980
LinkedIn	Germany	RISA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/risa-sicherheitsanalysen-gmbh	3
LinkedIn	Norway	VFK	https://www.linkedin.com/company/vefold-fylkeskommune	2,170

For up until the submission day of this deliverable, in Facebook, there already exist 93 persons or organisations who like HYPERIONS's Facebook page and 98 who follow it.

HYPERION's Twitter account already counts 139 followers.

HYPERION's LinkedIn has 17 followers.

LinkedIn Management

Particularly the European LinkedIn account will be used for academic dissemination. The roles assigned appear below:

Table 7: Academic dissemination via LinkedIn

Participant	Main post	Period
ICCS	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities. Articles referring to Project meetings, D2.2, D.2.3, D3.4, D7.7, D10.4	At least one every two months starting from month 1
FMI	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities Article referring to D3.1, D3.3	At least one every two months starting from month 2
RG	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities. Article referring to D2.1, D5.5, D7.3, D7.4, D8.7, D9.6, D10.1, D10.2, D10.5	At least one every two months starting from month 1
OSLOMET	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities Article referring to D4.6, D5.2	At least one every two months starting from month 2
NTUA	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities Article referring to D5.4, D6.1-6.4, D9.5, D9.9	At least one every two months starting from month 1
RISA	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities Article referring to D7.1, D7.2, D7.6	At least one every two months starting from month 2
UNIPD	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities Article referring to D4.2-4.5	At least one every two months starting from month 1
UGR	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities Article referring to D5.3, D6.5	At least one every two months starting from month 2
AUTH	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities Article referring to D2.4, D3.2, D3.5, D3.6, D5.1	At least one every two months starting from month 1
CYRIC	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities Article referring to D7.5, D8.1-8.6	At least one every two months starting from month 2

Participant	Main post	Period
IUAV	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities Article referring to D4.1	At least one every two months starting from month 1
VFK	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities	At least one every two months starting from month 2
CVI	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities	At least one every two months starting from month 1
DR	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities	At least one every two months starting from month 2
EFAD	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities	At least one every two months starting from month 1
ADG	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities	At least one every two months starting from month 2
IEMC	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities Article referring to 9.1-9.4, D9.7, D9.8, D10.3	At least one every two months starting from month 1
RED	General postings about events, project contents and supporting activities Article referring to D2.5, D5.6	At least one every two months starting from month 2

IEMC will link the above articles to Twitter and Facebook (recycling).

Interactive discussion on social media, social media campaigns

A social media campaign is a coordinated marketing effort to reinforce or assist with project's goal using one or more social media platforms. Campaigns differ from everyday social media efforts because of their increased focus, targeting and measurability.

Setting social media campaign goals:

A social media campaign should focus around the main project's goal.

Common goals for a social media campaigns include:

- Getting feedback from users;
- Building email stakeholders' lists;
- Increasing website traffic.

HYPERION team will organize at least one discussion on social media/ social media campaign by the end of the project.

The planning of the campaign will take place on the beginning of the last year of the project and it will be built on all the social media platforms.

Due to its interactive and real-time nature, digital creates the opportunity for people to be more open and connected to each other. As the social media become increasingly easy to understand and monitor, HYPERION will take a digital approach to spreading messages, attract support for project's goal and raise awareness.

Dialogue with networks, communities and associations

In addition to using the direct project sources (partners, project activities etc.), emphasis will, as mentioned above, be given to identify the sources that each potential stakeholder group is already tied into or most respects as an information source. Various media and tools can be used to deliver the project message, content and results to the target group, i.e. the ways or mechanisms used to send info to or communicate with the target group. Communication can be done by interpersonal contact (two-way communication) or through mass media (one-way communication). The one-way communication is associated with smaller audience, and lower costs, and more effort. Potentially large audience uses the credibility of the mass media.

Physical meetings

This Task concerns the planning of regular dissemination and communication events aimed at increasing awareness about HYPERION, showcasing project achievements and fostering the meeting of the HYPERION community with stakeholders. Such events will be preferably collocated with major conferences and symposia, and will be planned in the Dissemination and Communication Plan according to favorable opportunities.

All the activities will be disseminated through our social media accounts. The following figures are a small sample from the meetings and site activities that have been done to date.

The kick off meeting and the first PM meeting which were posted using the social media are following as sample.

Figure 4: HYPERION’s Kick off meeting in Athens, (Screenshot from the twitter account)

Figure 5: HYPERION’s first program management meeting in Rhodes, (Screenshot from the facebook account)

Also, the site activities are disseminated via our Social media accounts:

Figure 6: HYPERION’s activities carried out in Norway (Screenshot from the facebook account)

Personal photographs of people

Protection of personal rights are very important thus all consortium members are required to ask for the consent of people before taking any photograph during the PM events throughout the duration of the program. A Consent Form template is provided to them at the beginning of every event.

Table 8: List of 2020 Program meetings

Meeting	Location	Description	Dates
Plenary Meeting 2	Granada	Program Meeting	22-23/4/2020
Plenary Meeting 3	TBD	Program Meeting	TBD, October 2020

Participation in events, conferences and workshops

In the context of HYPERION, special attention is given to the project’s dissemination activities as well as in the event organisation and participation, throughout the course of the project. By effectively exploiting such opportunities, HYPERION aims to achieve wide acceptance and scale up of the project advances and results by a critical mass of

interested stakeholders and communities in the fields of interest. These opportunities are referred, but not limited, to the following:

- The participation in European and international conferences, specialized meetings, fora, working groups.
- The organization of dedicated events (e.g. Special Interested Sessions, demonstration events, International conference etc.)
- The publication in peer review scientific & technical journals, conference proceedings and high reputational magazines as already described previously in this document.

IEMC, as WP Leader, has proceeded, with the creation of a repository for HYPERION's events that are considered as valuable opportunities for the project. The repository includes an indicative list of proposed scientific journals and an indicative list of proposed upcoming European and international events and it is regularly updated mainly by WP Leader and by the consortium partners. In addition, HYPERION partners are regularly informed through emails about upcoming key opportunities so they will be able to benefit from them.

Table 9: List of proposed conferences in 2020

Conference Title	Date	Place
12th International Conference on Air Quality – Science and Application	9-13/3/2020	Thessaloniki, GR
Innovating Cities: Cultural Heritage in Action	14-15 May 2020	Bologna, IT
IUCN World Conservation Congress	11-19/6/2020	Marseille, FR
12th Nordic Symposium on Building Physics (NSB2020)	14– 17/6/2020	Tallinn, Estonia
GSCC 2020, Global Summit on Climate Change	15-16/6/2020	London, UK
44th Session of the World Heritage Committee	June/July 2020	Fuzhou, China
XV Congreso Internacional de Rehabilitación del Patrimonio Arquitectónico y Edificado	2-4/09/2020	Granada, Spain
8th ICSD 2020	9-10/9/2020	Roma Eventi, Congress Center
STONE2020	7-12/09/2020	Goettingen, Germany
International Conference on Metrology for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage	10 or 11/2020	Trento, IT

Final Event

A conference will be organised at the end of the project to demonstrate to a large number of stakeholders the system developed, and results achieved.

3.6 Key Communication Channels per Audience Group

Dissemination activities are of utmost importance both **during project duration** to create visibility and raise awareness within the scientific community, **and after the project end** to utilise the results and find ways to further continue and advance the related research. HYPERION gives special emphasis on the active and dynamic dissemination and exploitation of results to the relevant policy makers, governmental bodies and authorities:

- ✓ **Dissemination Activities to Policy-makers:** The HYPERION project will disseminate its results to the policy-makers such as the Directorates-General for Climate Action (DG CLIMA), for the Environment (DG ENV), for the Education and Culture (DG EAC), as well to the EC Joint Research Centre that provides European policy makers with scientific and technological advice. Activities may for example include participation of representatives from the above policy-makers' bodies to HYPERION

workshops/conferences etc. Special workshops will be organised in cooperation with ICOMOS and CIPA at the Headquarters of UNESCO in Paris.

- ✓ ***Dissemination Activities to relevant Ministries, Governmental Bodies and International Policy making Organisations:*** Ministries and Governmental bodies responsible for the management and protection of Cultural Heritage, for Civil Protection, for Infrastructure, for Environment and for the Economy will be presented, on a tactical schedule and at various levels (local/regional, national, international), of the ongoing results of the HYPERION project.
- ✓ ***The consortium will undertake all the necessary measures to present all the project results at the Sub-Committee for Culture, Diversity and Heritage of the Council of Europe in Strasbourg, France.***
- ✓ ***Dissemination Activities addressed to case studies:*** HYPERION will include focused dissemination activities to the project's Historic Cities, in coordination with local authorities and project participants, that will present, promote and provide feedback of the project's results to all interested communities for each Use Case, including Municipalities, local/regional governments, relevant Professional Chambers, relevant social groups, etc.
- ✓ ***Dissemination Activities to Superintendences/Ephorates:*** HYPERION plans the implementation of dissemination activities specific for Superintendences and Ephorates responsible for the management and protection of cultural heritage assets. These will not be limited to those from the selected Use Cases but will also include interested Superintendences and Ephorates from other CH sites that face similar threats from CC and natural hazards and can benefit from the results of the HYPERION project. HYPERION underlines the importance of the active participation of local stakeholders for the successful implementation of any mitigation and adaptation strategies and technologies that consider the needs of local communities. To succeed this, the local actors need to be actively informed of the HYPERION project's results and provide valuable feedback. HYPERION's results will be also presented to various international organizations relevant to CH protection and management, CC and natural hazards, and economic development. These include the International Council of Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS), the Organization of World Heritage Cities (OWHC) the International Committee for Documentation of Cultural Heritage (CIPA), the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction - Regional Office for Europe (UNISDR EUR), the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), the European Investment Bank (EIB), the International Finance Corporation – World Bank Group (IFC), the European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI) and the European Association of Archaeology.

Stakeholder mapping will contribute to map the target audience and it is an essential and basic step complementing the Communication activities of the project. In the process HYPERION team identify the individuals and groups that are likely to affect or be affected by HYPERION's proposed actions and results. Then, we group them based on their impact

and interest factors on the actions as well as the impact the actions may have on them. By assessing this information, the consortium gets a clearer vision on how the interests of those stakeholders should be addressed in the project communication and dissemination plan and relevant activities.

The following project target audiences are identified and categorized in connection to the project based on the figure below:

Figure 7: Categorization of target Audiences

Table 10: Target groups for the key communication channels

Channel	Audience				
	Scientific Community	Private Sector	Policy Makers	Public Bodies	General Public
Project website	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Newsletters					
Digital media, such as online newspapers and magazines		✓		✓	✓
Traditional media, such as TV, radio and press	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Communication and dissemination materials, such as roll up banners,	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

leaflets, posters, Short Animated Videos, etc.					
Annual magazines	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Press releases, Advertorials		✓	✓	✓	✓
Publications in scientific journals	✓	✓	✓		
Social media: Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Interactive discussion on social media, social media campaigns	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Dialogue with networks, communities and associations	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Physical meetings	✓		✓	✓	
Field events such as conferences, fairs, special sessions and workshops	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Pilots	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Final Event	✓	✓	✓	✓	

- Group 1 'Keep informed and 'satisfied": relevant national public bodies, EU, Other H2020 and related projects, Academia
- Group 2 'Manage closely': EU Commission Services, HYPERION participants, Partners
- Group 3 'Monitor': the general public, media, private sector, Applied technologies
- Group 4 'Keep informed and involved': expert panel, scientific community, workshop participants, decision and policy-makers.

Table 11: Plan for communication activities per target audience

Target Audiences	Category	Communication Channels	Frequency	Responsibility and task division
Scientific Community	Keep informed and involved'	Website	***	Research reports: WP leaders Other: All partners, as relevant
		Digital media,		
		Traditional media		
		Communication and dissemination materials.		
		Annual magazines		
		Press releases, Advertorials		
		Publications in scientific journals		
		Social media		
		Interactive discussion on social media, social media campaigns		
		Dialogue with networks, communities and associations		
Physical meetings				
Field events				
Pilots				
Final Event				
Private Sector	Monitor	Website	*	Coordination: ICCS, specific responsibilities: CYRIC, RISA, RG. All partners contribute as relevant (e.g. provide potential people to disseminate)
		Digital media,		
		Traditional media		
		Communication and dissemination materials.		
		Annual magazines		
		Press releases, Advertorials		
Publications in scientific journals				
Social media				

Target Audiences	Category	Communication Channels	Frequency	Responsibility and task division
		<p>Interactive discussion on social media, social media campaigns</p> <p>Dialogue with networks, communities and associations</p> <p>Field events</p> <p>Pilots</p> <p>Final Event</p>		
Policy Makers	Keep informed and involved	<p>Website</p> <p>Traditional media</p> <p>Communication and dissemination materials.</p> <p>Annual magazines</p> <p>Press releases, Advertorials</p> <p>Publications in scientific journals</p> <p>Social media</p> <p>Interactive discussion on social media, social media campaigns</p> <p>Dialogue with networks, communities and associations</p> <p>Physical meetings</p> <p>Field events</p> <p>Pilots</p> <p>Final Event</p>	**	<p>Coordination: ICCS, specific responsibilities: VFK, CVI, DG, EFAD, ADG.</p> <p>All partners contribute as relevant (to communicate important outputs/results in WPs)</p>
Public Bodies	Keep informed and 'satisfied'	<p>Website</p> <p>Traditional media</p> <p>Communication and dissemination materials.</p> <p>Annual magazines</p>	**	<p>Coordination: ICCS</p> <p>All partners contribute as relevant (to communicate important</p>

Target Audiences	Category	Communication Channels	Frequency	Responsibility and task division
		Press releases, Advertorials Publications in scientific journals Social media Interactive discussion on social media, social media campaigns Dialogue with networks, communities and associations Physical meetings Field events Pilots Final Event		outputs/results in WPs)
General Public	Monitor	Website Digital media, Traditional media Communication and dissemination materials. Press releases, Advertorials Social media Interactive discussion on social media, social media campaigns	**	RED prepares template and writes general press releases All partners adapt press releases to national context and disseminate to national media

3.6.1 Project's Key Messages

The core value of the nature of the dissemination is to communicate openly with the target audiences already defined. The key messages will be revised to better reflect what the audience should remember of the project.

The message component of the dissemination and communication strategy comprises the set of arguments, reasons and facts to be used to convince the targeted audiences of the value in using HYPERION results. Key messages are intended to deliver relevant and

meaningful content suited to communicate project’s value proposition to each of the target audiences.

3.6.2 Project's General Message

Since communication is the activity of delivering meaningful information, to successfully communicate key messages, HYPERION will deploy strategic methods:

- ✓ scientific results and applications’ developments will be fed in the communication strategy to share messages about the added value of the project. As such, the dissemination partners will collaborate with all project partners to share project progress;
- ✓ communication will reach-out new users and communities;
- ✓ HYPERION will define and communicate shared messages meaningful for all audiences:
- ✓ HYPERION messages will be ‘audience-specific’ and thus vary to address their respective, specific expectations and interest from the project
- ✓ messages will be continuously enriched through the project lifetime to reflect project progress, advancements and priorities as defined by the project or the external context;
- ✓ messages will be adapted to the technical/scientific level of the audience, and where necessary, a ‘lay’ approach and language will be adopted.

Table 12: HYPERION's Messages connected to project's objectives

MESSAGES	TECHNICAL/ SCIENTIFIC LEVEL AUDIENCE			
	Non-Scientific Community	Scientific Community	Local stakeholders	Media & scientific journals
<p>OBJECTIVE 1: HYPERION aims to leverage existing tools and services (e.g., climate/extreme events models, and their impacts, decay models of building materials, Copernicus services, etc.), novel technologies (terrestrial and satellite imaging for wide-area inspection, advanced machine learning, etc.) to deliver an integrated resilience assessment platform, addressing multi-hazard risk understanding, better preparedness, faster, adapted and efficient response, and sustainable reconstruction of historic areas.</p>				
<p>HYPERIONS’ integrated resilience assessment platform, helps addressing multi-hazard risk understanding, better preparedness, faster, adapted and efficient response, and</p>		✓	✓	✓

sustainable reconstruction of historic areas.				
HYPERION enhances resilience and reduced vulnerability of historic areas to climate change and other natural hazards	✓	✓	✓	✓

OBJECTIVE 2: HYPERION will take into account the local **eco-systems** in the CH areas, mapping out their interactions and following a truly **integrated/sustainable reconstruction** approach (*technical, social, institutional, environmental and economic level*), by incorporating **active communities participation** (using the PLUGGY social platform⁴) and by supporting new business models based on the concept of a “**load-balancing**” economy, (using an algorithm that acts like a “reverse proxy”, distributing client traffic across different companies within the same sector) and offering **financial risk-transfer tools** (insurance, Catastrophe-CAT-bonds⁵) that can ensure the immediate funds availability to fuel timely build-back-better efforts.

HYPERION develops a truly integrated/sustainable reconstruction approach in the Cultural Heritage areas	✓	✓	✓	✓
HYPERION foster improved reconstruction and economic and social recovery of historic areas by local authorities and communities using new knowledge and tools.	✓	✓	✓	✓

3.6.3 Project's Key Phrases

Supporting HYPERION project’s key Phrases:

Project’s Impact

- ✓ Multi-hazard risk understanding
- ✓ Faster, adapted, efficient response
- ✓ Better preparedness
- ✓ Sustainable reconstruction
- ✓ Quantitative impact assessment

⁴ The coordinating partner ICCS is also the project leader and the responsible for the social platform of the PLUGGY project: <https://www.pluggy-project.eu>

⁵ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/catastrophebond.asp>, [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Insurance-Linked_Securities_\(ILS\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Insurance-Linked_Securities_(ILS))

Project's components

In a similar way as with the objectives of the dissemination plan, the key messages will be deployed with a different focus along the project lifetime (see Chapter 2.2):

- ✓ Stage 1 (M1-M12): The project aims ...; The objectives of the project are ...; The potential impact of the project is ... [completed];
- ✓ Stage 2 (M6-M24): HYPERION team is working on the development of ... [mostly completed];
- ✓ Stage 3 (M18-M30): Preliminary results are ...;
- ✓ Stage 4 (M24-M42): The project achievements are ...; The impact of this developments is ...; Lessons-learned is...; Recommendations are ...

3.6.4 Project's Key Words

The keywords are essential for the scientific dissemination of the project and the primary means of communicating to search engines the topics the project is covering.

The following key words are given:

H2020, Climate Change, Cultural Heritage, Sustainable Reconstruction, Hygrothermal analysis, structural/geotechnical analysis, project, Novel Sensors, Resilience, innovation, Norway, Spain, Italy, Greece, Historic areas, Hazard events, Holistic resilience assessment platform

Meanwhile for supporting the dissemination and communication of the project in social media, tweetable key messages will be created and supported by the following HASHTAGS

#HYPERION, #CulturalHeritage, #Climatechange, #SustainableReconstruction, #resilience, #multihazardrisk, #NovelSensors, #innovation, #researchinfrastructure, #opendata, #HRAP, #ICOMOS, #ICCROM, #UNESCO, #EuropaNostra, #UNFCCC, #EuropeanHeritage, #owhc

AT(@) will be used for certain mass media channels: @icomoshellenic.gr, @kathimerini.gr, @ert.gr, @euronews.com which we will use.

3.6.5 Tailored Key Messages

Under the broad objection statements of HYPERION project (General Message), a varied realm of activities will take place. To convey the purposes and objectives of the project to the external audiences, the CDP encompasses a set of basic key messages that showcases HYPERION's concept and that will serve everybody for communicating the ultimate vision of the project.

Those messages, and their derivatives, are essential foundations for success of the CDP. They will be repeated constantly in all events where HYPERION will be present and will be launched repeatedly from the different platforms including social media used by the HYPERION project and specifically on the HYPERION website and Twitter account. Such a recurrence will ensure the correct understanding of the project aims and will contribute to the sustained attachment of related actors to it. Partnership will be encouraged to contribute by spreading those same words permanently.

Tailored key messages will be revised according to the stakeholders list to better reflect what the audience should remember of the project.

Stage 1 (M1-M12) KEY MESSAGES:

- ✓ HYPERION aims to introduce a research framework for downscaling the created climate and atmospheric composition and specific damage functions for Cultural Heritage materials.
- ✓ HYPERION is the development of a Decision Support System for Improved Resilience & Sustainable Reconstruction of historic areas to cope with Climate Change & Extreme Events based on Novel Sensors and Modelling Tools
- ✓ HYPERION involves researchers, citizen scientists, industry, decision makers and the society in general in sustainable reconstruction plans for the CH damages
- ✓ HYPERION vulnerability map visualizes the built heritage and cultural landscape under future climate scenarios
- ✓ HYPERION will be demonstrated to four European historic areas in Norway, Spain, Italy and Greece.

Tailored key messages will be extracted from project's results to be addressed to targeted groups in a way that encourages them to factor the outcomes into their work

3.7 Creating the project's community

3.7.1 Communities Outreach

One of the objectives of HYPERION project is that it takes into account the local ecosystems in the CH areas, mapping out their interactions and following a truly integrated/sustainable reconstruction approach (technical, social, institutional, environmental and economic level), **by incorporating active communities participation** (using the PLUGGY social platform⁶) and by supporting new business models based on the concept of a “load-balancing” economy, (using an algorithm that acts like a “reverse proxy”, distributing client traffic across different companies within the same sector) and offering financial risk-transfer tools (insurance, Catastrophe-CAT-bonds⁷) that can ensure the immediate funds availability to fuel timely build-back-better efforts.

As it is obvious from that one of the main challenges to be tackled in the project is **communities’ participatory** aspects to the overall resilience and reconstruction planning to be fostered.

For that reason, HYPERION is forming early in project’s cycle the **Communities of Practices (CoP)** (WP2)

This task will gather the current practices, needs and expectations from the end-users of HYPERION consortium (cities and cultural authorities), which will then be complemented with inputs to be obtained from the Advisory Board (AB) through different means (e.g., questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, workshops, combination of previous methods), as well as external stakeholders who will be invited by the project to formulate a sort of Communities of Practice group. In addition to the collection of inputs from the stakeholders, this task will carry out a deep analysis of all technical, regulatory and financial aspects that shall be considered for the development of HYPERION integrated system. This will include the analysis of EU and national relevant regulations and recommendations, and the compilation of most widespread current standards, practices, and solutions/tools related to operational and strategic management, risk analysis and decision-making for more resilient historic cities, considering the different points of view from public authorities, CH sites’ operators, and other relevant stakeholders.

3.7.2 Networking & Knowledge Exchange

To ensure the sustainability of the institutional changes towards Improved Resilience & Sustainable Reconstruction of historic areas to cope with Climate Change & Extreme Events and the impact of the project, it is critical to engage partners’ stakeholders strategically. Alliances are being pursued to gain support for actions within the partners’ organisations, for instance seeking opportunities for joint initiatives, but also to target a wider audience outside the partners’ organisations.

All partners are working to “bring all actors on board”, organising regular “core team” meetings, involving cultural heritage and novel technologies hubs in key decisions. These efforts are contributing to the development of new communities of practice within each performing partner, taking different forms depending on each partner’s peculiarities: groups of action, network, internal advisory groups etc.

⁶ The coordinating partner ICCS is also the project leader and the responsible for the social platform of the PLUGGY project: <https://www.pluggy-project.eu>

⁷ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/catastrophebond.asp>, [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Insurance-Linked_Securities_\(ILS\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Insurance-Linked_Securities_(ILS))

Joint initiatives may also be organised inside every partner (e.g. being involved in broader events with “corners” dedicated to Cultural Heritage protection and potential impact of Climate Change).

Furthermore, the partners are well-networked at a regional/national level with research governing bodies, scientific and professional associations and experts’ networks. The partners’ networks and relations will be harnessed to reach out to other stakeholders and disseminate the project’s learning beyond organisations.

This will be pursued by:

- ✓ engaging with other organizations to obtain a multiplier effect and increase the number of interested parties. As channels, partners are considering organising small events, webinars and/or personalised mailing to key stakeholders.
- ✓ participating in H2020 networking and mutual exchange events, targeting stakeholders on a national or international level
- ✓ Maintenance of a permanent flow of information
- ✓ Developing partnerships with other projects and other European organisations engaged in supporting research and innovation
- ✓ Contribution to capacity building. Input from stakeholders about new developments can feed into capacity building by acquiring and channeling the information that will contribute to innovations.
- ✓ Interrelation with global organizations for expanding level of scope.

Additional activities potentially useful to leverage the stakeholder engagement are indicative:

- ✓ invitation to subscribe to HYPERION newsletter,
- ✓ invitation to events,
- ✓ invitation to share contents to be published on HYPERION website;
- ✓ interaction via social media;
- ✓ interviews to be published on HYPERION channels;
- ✓ Participation of partners at events of external stakeholders.

The communication managers of related projects funded under H2020 will be invited to share in their newsletters details of the HYPERION project and the link where their partners and stakeholders can sign up for different media.

3.7.3 Channels to reach specific communities

Apart from the Communication channels mentioned above, specific communities will be reached via the Development of the Communities’ Engagement ICT Tool.

ICCS will be responsible for the development of the ICT tool for enabling Communities engagement in HYPERION. The tool will be based on PLUGGY’s Social Platform and Curatorial Tool, an open source platform specializing on the preservation and promotion of everyday all-around heritage, using crowdsourced techniques.

The HYPERION Communities' Engagement ICT tool will utilize PLUGGY's extendibility capabilities in order to create a) an extension to PLUGGY's curatorial tool to enable citizens to create stories about the deterioration of CH sites, geo-locate the sites and also provide specific information, b) an external source plugin to allow PLUGGY to retrieve data from the Galileo imagery, the Copernicus data and Euro-CORDEX and c) a specialized mobile phone app, also utilizing PLUGGY's API, for the retrieval of the stories created in (a) and their innovative presentation to users, in order for them to experience the story and better understand the changes imposed by climate change and extreme events. The task will produce a first draft of the software for (a) and (b) at M20 and their final versions at M28 along with (c).

3.7.4 Involving communities: The Approach

The following guidelines underline the approach to involve communities in HYPERION:

- a) Recognition of current environment to identify leading forces

Engagement will be based on strong foundations by recognizing and categorizing all potential players that may have a role in establishing the state-of-the-art of the stakeholder landscape relevant for HYPERION (see Communities of Practices).

- b) Reference to existing contexts for action, coherent policies and joint support of protocols

In its efforts to deploy the project's approach to stakeholder engagement, several European frameworks that underpin societal challenges will be engaged. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), as specified by the European Commission, the FAIR principles for accessible, and reusable data, among others, will be at the core of all discussions held with stakeholders and will be raised as drivers of the innovation process. Furthermore, the vision of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) will be also a powerful setup that HYPERION will be working towards.

- c) Constant exchange of information

The importance of engaging with stakeholders is to induce steady information flows from which the project partners can draw the necessary knowledge and information. This guarantees that the stakeholders, and major partners, will have actual influence on the outcome of the project by providing input through consultations, the events and via the organised conferences.

- d) Efficient communication

Given that targeted audiences are diverse and might be placed outside the domain of the project, a strong effort will have to be devoted to engaging the stakeholders and, specifically, the public domain that could push innovation on policy making. To respect

their position, level of involvement and potential time constraints, HYPERION seeks to ensure that stakeholders will benefit equally from their participation in events and surveys. In order both parties to benefit from engagement encounters, a two-way flow of useful information will be deployed. It provides a win-win scenario for both project community and stakeholders.

3.8 HYPERION Roll up Banner

Hyperion

A resilience assessment platform, addressing multi-hazard risk understanding, better preparedness, faster/adapted/efficient response and sustainable reconstruction of historic areas.

Hyperion Components

- Technologies**
 - Advanced Machine Learning
 - Participative Cultural Heritage
- Services**
 - Copernicus
 - Euro-CORDEX
 - Environmental
 - Weather
 - Cadaster
- Tools**
 - Terrestrial Imaging
 - Satellite Imaging
 - Wide Area Inspection
 - Climate/Extreme Events models
 - Decay Models of materials

Impact

- Multi-hazard risk understanding
- Better preparedness
- Faster, adapted, efficient response
- Sustainable reconstruction
- Quantitative impact assessment

The partners

Learn more at: www.hyperion-project.eu

Project Duration
 June 2019 – November 2022
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This work is part of the HYPERION project. The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 821052.

Figure 8: Roll up banner

4. Detailed Dissemination procedures and activity report

IEMC has provided the consortium with detailed Dissemination procedures to be followed during the implementation of the different activities, with the basic objective of producing high-quality communication materials, avoiding overlaps and disclosure of confidential information.

The publication or presentation of work done within the framework of HYPERION or any other communication and dissemination activity related to the HYPERION project has to be approved beforehand by the HYPERION Project Coordinator and the Project Coordination Team (PCT).

In ANNEX 1, the step by step procedures for partners' dissemination activities is presented in detail.

In addition, to ensure constant monitoring and tracking of the dissemination and communication activities carried out by HYPERION consortium, a Dissemination activities report has been set up, to be filled in within ten working days after the realisation of the approved dissemination activity, accompanied by the presented dissemination material (final paper, presentation, poster etc.).

The detailed Dissemination procedures, together with the Dissemination activities requests table and the Dissemination activities report, are available on project's repository platform - REDMINE.

5. Role of partners

Table 13: Dissemination plans for each one of the *HYPERION* partners

Partner	Dissemination Activities' Plan
ICCS	ICCS will use its large network of partners to disseminate the ideas, developments and results of <i>HYPERION</i> . These partners will emanate from the following relevant project: SCENT, WeObserve, Cirf4Life, NextGen and PLUGGY, where ICCS is directly involved. Within that frame, a series of co-organized workshops could be organized. Moreover, ICCS will employ its social media accounts to further communicate <i>HYPERION</i> news to the relevant communities and general public
FMI	FMI will use FMI web pages, press releases and twitter for dissemination. The Finnish portal on adaptation to CC, operated by FMI, will be used to spread information about the project outcomes. FMI is part of the consortia (EU-Copernicus Info-sessions) responsible for training and disseminating related to Copernicus services (climate, air quality) that will be used as project dissemination channel
RG	Presentations in international workshops and conferences; whitepapers drafting, contribution to dissemination material, contribution to relevant open standards bodies
OSLOMET	OSLOMET will disseminate project results by publishing them in international peer-reviewed scientific journals & international/regional conferences in the field of building physics, HAM, building simulation and materials. The project activities and results will be uploaded on OSLOMET's websites and social media and on the three supporting partners from Norway. A special webpage will be created for the purposes of open access to the HT tool along with guidelines and project results relevant to its performance.
NTUA	NTUA will use publications to widely disseminate project results to the relevant channels under the CH inspection, CV methodologies, multi-spectral/hyperspectral imaging and ML, DInSAR methodologies, resilience and vulnerability assessment. NTUA will also use its established channels for disseminating in the CV-based applications, structural/resilience assessment entities, non-destructive testing and industrial users through newsletters, relevant conferences and EC events.
RISA	The initial proposal of RISA for disseminating <i>HYPERION</i> follows 4 different lines: 1) Promoting <i>HYPERION</i> 's website: RISA plans to reserve a public accessible space for promoting project ideas, including groups of discussion about topics of interest or related with <i>HYPERION</i> . 2) Liaison with other cultural related projects within the scope of H2020, especially those in which RISA is also directly or indirectly involved into. This will give

	<p>very quick and efficient interactions for a fruitful information interchange, and cooperation on common ideas that could serve for both projects. 3) Attendance to Journals, events, congresses to promote HYPERION project: RISA will contribute with papers, presentations and dissemination activities on those relevant events to this CH-oriented topic. In particular: a) Attendance and paper presentations to annual congresses; b) Attendance and paper presentations to annual congresses coping with CH within contents; c) other events and workshops.</p>
UNIPD	<p>UNIPD will disseminate in the scientific community at relevant conferences, at meetings organised in the frame of the project, and on open access papers in ISI international journals in the field of cultural heritage, materials science, archaeometry, conservation and restoration. Dissemination will also be addressed to public authorities and a wider audience in relevant conferences, persuaded that also people in the society should be aware of the CH threaten and protection issues.</p>
UGR	<p>UGR will disseminate the influence of CC in CH and the CV-based application creating a free-elective course (1 credit ECTS) after the end of the project, it will be repeated at least during 5 years. The course will be open to students of the Architecture and Civil Engineering Schools and to professionals. Journal publications and congresses will also be used.</p>
AUTH	<p>Dissemination in the scientific community will mainly include submission of publications in scientific journals in the field of climate, meteorology and atmospheric physics, scientific reports to be prepared within the frame of the project, as well as presentations of project results in relevant conferences. HYPERION will also be presented in a dedicated section on the web page of the Laboratory of Heat Transfer and Environmental Engineering.</p>
CYRIC	<p>CyRIC will exploit its participation in the Business Innovation Center (BIC) network for disseminating project results towards a vast network of possible business users. The project results will also be disseminated through presentations and printed material distribution in events that the company regularly organises in their privately-owned Incubator (Gravity Ventures). Finally, a video will be prepared for explaining the project concept to the general audience. The video will be used by the company (and the entire consortium) for dissemination through the web, social media and the press.</p>
IUAV	<p>The project results will be mainly disseminated by means of scientific publications submitted to ISI international journals in the field of cultural heritage, archaeometry, conservation, restoration and materials sciences. Data collected will be also presented in relevant conferences as well as shared with local public authorities operating for the conservation of the Venetian historical buildings.</p>

VFK	VFK's official Web site and Kulturarv's own FB-channel will be used to publish and disseminate the concept, ongoing work and results from the project. In addition, talks and presentations will be given to regional and local politicians and policymakers in Vestfold County and Tønsberg Municipality. Attendance and presentations in relevant congresses, seminars and workshops at national and international level will also be given.
CVI	The City of Venice will work in close collaboration with the project local partners (IUAV, UNIPD and the associate partner Venice's Superintendence for CH) to disseminate and raise awareness about project activities and results among decision makers, experts in the field and stakeholders. The aims are to get well informed of the major achievements and then to encourage them to use our outputs so as to improve the interventions to protect Venice's cultural heritage from the effects of climate change. General dissemination activities will contribute to grant project visibility to the citizens.
DR	Social networks, the city's website, local media portals, meetings with relevant stakeholders and liaisons with other cities through the existing networks.
EFA DOD	EFADOD, assisted by NTUA, aims to disseminate and raise awareness about project activities and results among decision makers, experts in the field and stakeholders.
ADG	ADG will use its own means to communicate the results: local newspaper and TV. The results of the project will be also communicated to the Association of Architects.
UGR	UGR along with ADG will organize a congress, at national level, to communicate HYPERION results to the professionals involved in CH maintenance.
IEMC	Dissemination through UNESCO channels, participation in conferences and relevant events, promotion to relevant stakeholders.
RED	<p>Part of RED staff is involved in academic activities and scientific research, thus the team will be able to disseminate the results of the projects through teaching activity, submission of publications to scientific journals and presentation at conferences in the field of disaster risk management and reduction.</p> <p>RED will also exploit its connections with insurance companies to raise awareness about the HYPERION's project innovative output and methodologies. HYPERION will also be presented in a dedicated section on RED's web page.</p>

6. EVALUATION & MONITORING ACTIVITIES – KPIs

The effectiveness of HYPERION’s communication and dissemination activities will be periodically measured. Periodic evaluation is considered very important to guarantee that all identified target audiences are properly reached and provided with appropriate information and content on project’s assets and to generate feedback and get insights on what works and what needs refinement.

Therefore, IEMC, being the WP9 Leader regularly monitor progress against KPIs as set out in the project’s DoA.

Table 14: List of the main HYPERION Communication and Dissemination Activities & set KPIs

Activity	Description	When
Creation of recognisable brand identity	Development of the HYPERION brand: To ensure the impact of the project HYPERION will develop an EU wide recognisable brand that visually translates the project idea and concept in all outreach materials and events.	M3 (done)
KPI	1 project logo, brand guidelines, HYPERION templates, illustrations and graphics	
Communication kit	Leaflets and posters based on HYPERION’s visual identity to be produced gradually until M12. This material will be distributed at congresses, workshops, exhibitions and important events. Around major milestones (M12), e-Newsletters will be sent to the HYPERION’s stakeholder network (CoP) and to relevant initiatives (H2020 and beyond). A Video to present the main objectives and target outcomes of HYPERION will be produced in the early stages of the project. A video will be also produced to showcase our proposed HYPERION solution in the various events.	M01- M42
KPI	2 leaflets, 1 poster, 2 animation video and 3 Newsletter issues.	

Dedicated project and code websites	Launch and maintenance of the HYPERION website in M5. Its basic objective is to create an easily accessible public platform for dissemination of deliverables, open access publications, presentations, newsletter issues etc. Interactivity and updated content will attract attention and repeated visits. In addition a GitHub ⁸ open software development site will be created to attract research community participation and long-term engagement in the creation of the SG simulator interfaces, the MHVAT toolkit and the HRAP engine.	M5-42, for min 5 years after end of project
KPI	1 official project website; 10,000 visitors per year combined	
Social media channels	Social media will be used to reach the target audience frequently and cost-efficiently, and to strengthen the HYPERION stakeholder network (Communities of Practice- Task 2.1). Basic information on HYPERION and its concept will also be disseminated through the partners' existing social networking pages as well as the H2020 social media accounts.	M01-M42
KPI	Active HYPERION ResearchGate, LinkedIn, Facebook & Twitter accounts. At least 200 members per account by M42. At least 4 announcements per partner in individual social media accounts; at least 6 announcements in H2020 social media sites. In total, minimum 150 posts/year expected.	
Conference presentations	HYPERION will have presentations and demos in relevant international conferences and other events. We will also organise special sessions and other project events at well-known transport conferences.	M12-M42
KPI	Minimum 3 presentations per year targeting at least 10 presentations in total	

⁸ GitHub software development platform: <https://github.com/>

Peer-reviewed publications	Effort will be made to publish papers in well-respected and highly rated peer-reviewed journals. This task will be undertaken mostly by the research partners, and the publications will cover several project fields of work. Particular effort will be made to secure Open Access (OA) to all interested persons, mainly through the project website but also through respective OA repositories such as OpenAIRE.	M18- M42
KPI	At least 2 publications in scientific ISI journals	
EU dissemination networks & Mass Media	The consortium, always in close collaboration with the EC personnel, will disseminate the project vision and main results through various means offered by the EU, e.g., Horizon Magazine, research*EU results magazine, EuroNews TV etc. Partners will also investigate possibilities to participate in EU research conferences and public events, e.g., EU City Forum (2019), Open Door Days and H2020 Researchers Nights events.	M06-M42
KPI	At least 2 press releases per year; at least 4 media articles in popular and/or specialised media; At least 1 interview on Radio and/or TV; Participation in prioritised EU events	
Training & Demo events	Training sessions in relevant events or online: HYPERION puts emphasis on “educating” the communities and relevant organisations about the need for additional advanced research to cover their requirements.	M24-M42
KPI	≥ 1 online sessions, minimum 3 Training Events; 3 Pilot demonstrations; Training package; Attendance ≥ 50 non-specialist attendees	
Final Event	A conference will be organised at the end of the project to demonstrate to a large number of stakeholders the system developed and results achieved.	Around M42 (based on planning)
KPI	1 HYPERION conference (more than 80 participants in total); Conference proceedings and report;	

7. Communication and Dissemination's plan roadmap

The following table shows the communication and dissemination roadmap for the first 36 months of the project with the WP9 deliverables and tasks Gantt and the KPI to be achieved.

The figure also shows which the current situation in M6 is:

Deliverable	Goal	Progr ess	M 1	M 2	M 3	M 4	M 5	M 6	M 7	M 8	M 9	M 10	M 11	M 12	M 13	M 14	M 15	M 16	M 17	M 18	M 19	M 20	M 21	M 22	M 23	M 24	M 25	M 26	M 27	M 28	M 29	M 30	M 31	M 32	M 33	M 34	M 35	M 36			
9.1																																									
Corporate ID & templates	1	100 %	█	█	█																																				
9.2																																									
Project Website	1	100 %	█	█	█	█	█																																		
Web visits	10,000/year	1%																																							
Twitter account	1	100 %	█																																						
Twitter-Followers	200	56%																																							
LinkedIn Account	1	100 %	█																																						
LinkedIn-Connections	200	9%																																							
Facebook Account	1	100 %	█																																						
Research Gate	1	0%																																							
9.3																																									
DCP (v1)	1	100 %						█																																	
Established relation w/EU projects	Goal	1%																																							
9.4																																									
leaflets	2	0%																																							

Deliverable	Goal	Progress	M 1	M 2	M 3	M 4	M 5	M 6	M 7	M 8	M 9	M 10	M 11	M 12	M 13	M 14	M 15	M 16	M 17	M 18	M 19	M 20	M 21	M 22	M 23	M 24	M 25	M 26	M 27	M 28	M 29	M 30	M 31	M 32	M 33	M 34	M 35	M 36				
poster	1	0%											🎯																													
animation video	2	0%											🎯																													
Newsletter issues	7	0%																																								
Conference presentations	10	0%																																								
Peer-reviewed publications	2	0%																																								
EU dissem. networks & Mass Media	Goal	0%																																								
Training & Demo events	Goal	0%																																								
Final Event	1	0% (M4 2)																																								
9.5																																										
Annual Magazine	1	0%																																								
9.6																																										
Report on Standards & Liaison Activities	1	0% (M4 2)																																								

7.1 Acknowledgement

All the communication and dissemination activities must include that the project has received funding from the EU using the EU emblem, the funding information text and the disclaimer excluding Commission responsibility as showed below:

HYPERION project is co-funded by the European Union (EU). Any dissemination, communication and publication materials (in any form, including on-line or electronic forms) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results, must clearly acknowledge the receipt of EU funding through:

The display of the EU emblem

The acknowledgment of EU funding by including the following text:

For communication and dissemination activities:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research & innovation programme under grant agreement no 821054.”

For infrastructure, equipment and major results:

“This [infrastructure] [equipment] [insert type of result] is part of the HYPERION project. HYPERION has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research & innovation programme under grant agreement no 821054.”

A complementary disclaimer will be also included whenever using the funding logo.

“The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of (name of the implementing partner) and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.”

Another complementary disclaimer will be also included in publications as well as when producing a communication or dissemination material.

“Content reflects only the authors’ view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”

For correct use of the EC emblem, partners or external specialists might use the following link: European flag:

http://europa.eu/about-eu/basic-information/symbols/flag/index_en.htm

8. CONCLUSION

The final produced document presenting HYPERION dissemination and communication plan, is a fundamental point for the WP9 entire strategy and moreover for the entire project, since it gives a precise status of the activities done or to be done defining all specific actions.

Considering its necessary implementation and updates during the project's lifespan (project development, possible changing etc.), it is a living document to be shared between partners so that each consortium member can suggest and insert activities / participation in events /press and media activities done by itself or by its own partners.

9. REFERENCES

1. European Commission (2019), "*What is the difference between dissemination, exploitation and communication?*", Retrieved on 12/2019 from <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/fag/933>
2. *Communicating and promoting your project*, retrieved Nov 2019 https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm
3. https://ec.europa.eu/easme/sites/easme-site/files/howtocommunicateyourproject_vertical.pdf
4. <https://whc.unesco.org/en/climatechange/>

10. ANNEXES

ANNEX 1 - COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION PROCEDURES

1. Description and purpose

The publication or presentation of work done within the framework of HYPERION or any other communication and dissemination activity related to the HYPERION project has to be approved beforehand by the HYPERION Project Coordinator and the Project Coordination Team (PCT).

2. Basic objective of the procedures

- Produce high quality HYPERION publications and presentations;
- Avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information;
- Keeping an appropriate registry of the dissemination activities of the project.

3. Step by step procedure:

1. At least two weeks before the publisher's or organizer's deadline for submitting a paper or proposal for presentation, the initiator of the dissemination activity:
 - registers the planned activity by adding a new row at the bottom of the list of Dissemination requests (available at: https://redmine.iccs.gr/projects/hyperion/dmsf?folder_id=7189) and uploads the updated excel at the same folder;
 - stores the abstract, paper or poster at: (https://redmine.iccs.gr/projects/hyperion/dmsf?folder_id=7198);
 - informs via email the HYPERION WP9 Leader (pyannakopoulos@yahoo.co.uk) and ICCS Communications Manager (sophia.adam@iccs.gr) about its inputs.
2. The WP Leader or ICCS Communications Manager sends the request within 2 days to the PCT for approval, modification or rejection;
3. The PCT members have to reply to the HYPERION WP9 Leader (pyannakopoulos@yahoo.co.uk) and ICCS Communications Manager

(sophia.adam@iccs.gr) within 5 working days; no response is considered as approval;

4. The WP9 Leader informs the initiator about the decision.

In case of:

a) *Approval*: The initiator may proceed with the submission and realization of the planned dissemination activity;

b) *Conflict/objection*: Any PCT member can object to the proposed dissemination activity, for example in cases of overlaps or in risk of disclosure of restricted or confidential information. The issue is discussed among the Coordinator, the WP9 Leader, ICCS Communications Manager and the involved partners;

**If a conflict is created or further material is needed then WP9 Leader informs the partner and requires modifications or additions. Then the material is proposed again to WP9 Leader and ICCS Communications Manager and if significant changes that might provoke conflicts among partners' interests must be made, the previous procedure is followed.

Within 10 working days after the realization of the approved dissemination activity, the initiator of the dissemination activity:

1. adds it in the bottom of the list in the appropriate sheet in the excel, entitled "Conducted Disseminations Activities for reporting" (https://redmine.iccs.gr/projects/hyperion/dmsf?folder_id=7187) and uploads the updated excel at the same folder https://redmine.iccs.gr/projects/hyperion/dmsf?folder_id=7187
2. completes a dissemination report (available at: https://redmine.iccs.gr/projects/hyperion/dmsf?folder_id=7187) and uploads it at https://redmine.iccs.gr/projects/hyperion/dmsf?folder_id=7187
3. uploads the final paper, presentation, poster, or other presented material in the appropriate folder within https://redmine.iccs.gr/projects/hyperion/dmsf?folder_id=7187
4. uploads photos from the activity, if relevant, at https://redmine.iccs.gr/projects/hyperion/dmsf?folder_id=7187

5. informs via email the HYPERION WP9 leader (pyannakopoulos@yahoo.co.uk) and ICCS Communications Manager (sophia.adam@iccs.gr)

NOTE:

If partners wish to present or release material already approved as public presentation and material then no formal approval is required, but the HYPERION WP9 leader (pyannakopoulos@yahoo.co.uk) and ICCS Communications Manager (sophia.adam@iccs.gr) has to be informed.

In case a partner wishes to organize a workshop or special event related to HYPERION, then the approval of the HYPERION WP9 leader (pyannakopoulos@yahoo.co.uk) and ICCS Communications Manager (sophia.adam@iccs.gr) and the information of the Coordinator and the PCT is also needed 2 months before the realization of this dissemination activity.

** For non-European travels the Project Officer (PO) should be informed and an approval from his side is required. Please fill-in the Non-European Travel Report Template (https://redmine.iccs.gr/projects/hyperion/dmsf?folder_id=7189) at least two months before the travel and send the form to the Project Coordinator (a.amditis@iccs.gr), so as to inform the EC. For possible enquiry by the auditors in the future it is recommended to keep the form and EC's response with the respective travel documents.

4. Dissemination of another party's unpublished results

In case a partner wishes to include another partner's results in a dissemination activity (which are not published), it needs to first obtain that partner's prior written approval. The mere absence of the foregoing objection is not considered as an approval. The dissemination shall be governed by the procedure as described above.

5. Publications in open-access platforms and journals and presentations at multiplier events

In Horizon 2020 Open Access to Scientific Peer Reviewed Publications has been anchored as an 'underlying principle'. This means that it has become obligatory for all

projects to ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results (free, online access for any user). Affordable and easy access to scientific information is very important for the scientific community itself, but also increasingly important for innovative small businesses. Improving access to scientific information is also about increasing openness and transparency, which are essential features of Responsible Research and Innovation and contributes to better policy-making.

Each beneficiary from an Horizon 2020 grant must deposit the work in a repository and make it Open Access (after an embargo if necessary) – regardless of whether it has been published in an Open Access Journal or not. There are two main, non-exclusive ways of making publications and data Open:

1. through self-archiving in repositories or
2. through publishing in an Open Access Journal (you can find a list of reliable Open Access journals in the Directory of Open Access Journals ([DOAJ](#))).

This obligation of us is also well-described in HYPERION's GA, article 2.2.2.1. Data Management Plan (DMP), Data Sharing and Exploitation Policies, to ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications.

Therefore, to provide Open Access, HYPERION participants are asked:

(i) to deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications. (Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.)

(ii) to ensure open access (OA) as follows:

- Gold OA: researchers can publish in open access journals (paid open access, processing charges). OA must be granted at the latest on publication.
- Green OA: researchers can deposit the final peer-reviewed manuscript in a repository of their choice, access is granted after an embargo period. OA must be granted within six months of publication.

(iii) to ensure open access to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publications.

You are free to deposit your peer-reviewed publications in any institutional, thematic or centralized online archive you consider most appropriate. However, all HYPERION related publications must be reported continuously to the EC under one of the following options:

- Preferred options: OpenAIRE (Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe, www.openaire.eu) or ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org/>): Publications registered via OpenAIRE will directly link to the H2020 project concerned and automatically display all relevant information for reporting. Publications registered via ZENODO will directly linked to OpenAIRE as well.
- DOI: Publications not accessible via OpenAIRE must be reported using the digital object identifier persistently linking to the article in a repository.
- Other: Publications not accessible via OpenAIRE or DOI must be provided and full reference data entered manually.

More detailed guidelines are available here:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

More infos:

https://www.slideshare.net/OpenAIRE_eu/webinar-on-open-access-to-publications-in-horizon-2020

<https://www.openaire.eu/item/webinars-h2020-policies-on-open-access-and-research-data>

6. Acknowledgement

HYPERION project is co-funded by the European Union (EU). Any dissemination, communication and publication materials (in any form, including on-line or electronic forms) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results, must clearly acknowledge the receipt of EU funding through:

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“Content reflects only the authors’ view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”

For correct use of the EC emblem, partners or external specialists might use the following link: https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en

For any additional information or clarification you might need, please contact the WP9 Leader.